

Social Media: A Mighty Appliance in Today's World

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Abstract:- In today 's world *social media* is a word, that everyone is used to. A technology that helps us to create, share our very varied knowledge, experiences, interests and other expressions via networks and communication that are not only virtual, but sometimes misleading too. This media as such is so powerful and like a double-edged sword, and thus therefore, sometimes referred to as Fourth Power of the present-day world. This is so because, at one place it is helping people to connected themselves with each other in some positive ways. But if one flips the coin, this very social media acts like demon which is engulfing the mind of our future generation in a negative manner, playing havoc in their overall development-social, mental and physical well-being.

Keywords:- Social Media, Technology, Society and Future Generation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Today's world is a fast growing 21st century world and it is wholly and globally connected through with advancement of science and innovative technologies. As a result, distances have either vanished or shortened, giving way to globalization and revolutionized means of technology.

Technologies are set ups and applications, in the form of material and immaterial, having some values. There exist varied forms like

- Material technology
- Electric technology
- Nuclear technology
- Biotechnology
- Electronic technology
- Medical technology
- Mechanical technology
- Information technology &
- Communication technology

A technology is something that helps us to create, share our very varied knowledge, experiences, interests and other expressions via networks and communication that are not only virtual, but sometimes misleading too. Information & communication technology inculcate within them one of the most prized possessions of modern- day humans today, that is *social media*.

Social media, a part of media, a marketing tool that helps us interact or facilitates conversations with people and community, links with the audiences and also builds relationships.

A concept that started in 1990s, as a mashup combination of technology, communication and media, was developed by Ted Leonsis & Steve Case at AOL. It was thought that social media could help people find place for communicate, get entertained and participate in social environment.

Kepios analysis shows that there were 4.55 billion social media users around the world in October 2021, equating to 57.6 % of the total global population (global social media stats). It is seen as a strong platform, with 409 million new users in previous year, that equates to 9.9 % of annual growth or say adding 13 users every second.

A typical user of social media generally uses or visits on an average 6.7 different platforms every month and spends on an average of close to 2 ½ hours each day on social media. Or to be specific roughly spends 15% of their waking lives using it. When added together in world scenario, for each day (10 billion hours), it accounts to a total of 1.2 million years of human existence.

Fig 1: - Social Media Users around the world. Source: - Kepeois Analysis 2021

Amongst all the platforms of social media, face book is most sought for, with 2.895 billion users, followed by You tube, What’s App and so on.

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SOCIAL MEDIA PLATFORMS: USER OVERLAPS
 PERCENTAGE OF USERS AGED 16 TO 64* OF EACH SOCIAL MEDIA PLATFORM (OUTSIDE OF CHINA) WHO ALSO USE OTHER SOCIAL MEDIA PLATFORMS
 ⚠️ THE QUESTIONS THAT INFORM THIS CHART HAVE CHANGED, SO VALUES ARE NOT COMPARABLE WITH THOSE PUBLISHED IN PREVIOUS REPORTS

	UNIQUE TO PLATFORM	ALSO USING FACEBOOK	ALSO USING YOUTUBE	ALSO USING INSTAGRAM	ALSO USING REDDIT	ALSO USING SNAPCHAT	ALSO USING TWITTER	ALSO USING TIKTOK	ALSO USING PINTEREST	ALSO USING LINKEDIN
FACEBOOK USERS	0.7%	100.0%	75.2%	77.6%	13.8%	32.2%	49.2%	44.9%	36.6%	31.9%
YOUTUBE USERS	1.0%	79.9%	100.0%	77.8%	15.3%	29.9%	52.1%	42.6%	38.6%	31.9%
INSTAGRAM USERS	0.1%	83.1%	78.8%	100.0%	14.9%	36.7%	55.0%	47.8%	40.7%	31.9%
REDDIT USERS	0.1%	81.4%	79.2%	82.5%	100.0%	50.0%	73.0%	51.4%	59.4%	50.1%
SNAPCHAT USERS	0.1%	83.7%	79.2%	88.9%	21.9%	100.0%	62.8%	58.4%	51.0%	38.9%
TWITTER USERS	0.2%	83.8%	80.9%	87.5%	21.0%	41.2%	100.0%	51.9%	44.6%	40.2%
TIKTOK USERS	0.1%	85.0%	81.3%	84.4%	16.4%	42.6%	57.7%	100.0%	44.4%	31.7%
PINTEREST USERS	0.1%	83.0%	80.5%	86.3%	22.7%	44.5%	59.5%	53.2%	100.0%	42.2%
LINKEDIN USERS	0.3%	88.4%	78.3%	82.5%	23.4%	41.6%	65.4%	46.5%	51.5%	100.0%

SOURCE: GWI (Q2 2021). SEE GWI.COM FOR MORE DETAILS. *NOTES: ONLY INCLUDES USERS AGED 16 TO 64. DOES NOT INCLUDE USERS IN CHINA. VALUES REPRESENT THE USERS OF THE PLATFORM IN THE LEFT-HAND COLUMN WHO ALSO USE THE PLATFORM IN THE ROW AT THE TOP OF EACH COLUMN. PERCENTAGES IN THE "UNIQUE TO PLATFORM" COLUMN REPRESENT USERS WHO SAY THEY DO NOT USE ANY OTHER SOCIAL NETWORK OR MESSENGER SERVICE, INCLUDING PLATFORMS NOT LISTED IN THIS TABLE. ⚠️ COMPARABILITY ADVISORY: SURVEY CHANGES.

Fig 2: - Social Media Users overlap. Source: - Kepeois Analysis 2021

These different varieties of social media platforms have a compelling story to deliver, when it comes to users and audiences, as these overlap in usages and largely depends upon user's needs.

Table 1: - Source : <https://www.theglobalstatistics.com> > [Indian social media.com](#)

Total population in India	1.39 billion
Active social media users in India	0.448 billion
Number of Internet users in India	0.624 billion
Social Media Users via Mobiles in India	0.444 billion
Number of Mobile Internet users in India	0.572 billion

When it comes to Indian perspective, it is observed that social media is like a melting pot of ideas for them and more specifically, it acts like a voice of ignored/ unheard ones.

Table 2: - Source : <https://www.theglobalstatistics.com> > [Indian social media.com](#)
Most Used Social Media Platforms in India 2021

	PERCENTAGE	IN NUMBERS
Annual growth in active social media users.	31.2%	78 million +
Annual growth of Internet users	8.2%	44 million +

Table 3: - Source : <https://www.theglobalstatistics.com> > [Indian social media.com](#)
Top 3 Devices being used in India for social media networking

PLATFORM	PERCENTAGE
Youtube	85.80%
Facebook	75.70%
Instagram	70.60%
Twitter	50.60%
LinkedIn	37.70%
Pinterest	34.30%
Reddit	22.10%

Table 4: - Source : <https://www.theglobalstatistics.com> > [Indian social media.com](#)

DEVICE	PERCENTAGE
Mobile Phone	76.60%
Laptop & Desktop	22.90%
Tablet	0.50%

The number of mobile connections in India are 1.1 billion. The mobile connection as per the percentage of total population is 79%. There are about 0.91 billion prepaid connections which is about 82.6% of the total connection. The postpaid connection is much less with 0.19 billion. This is about 17.4% of the total connection. The broadband connections as percentage of all mobile connections are 67.90%. 650.7 billion hours is the total hours spent using the mobile phone. The total number of mobile apps downloaded is 24.27 billion.

➤ *Most Used Mobile Apps by Category in India*

Table 5: - Source : <https://www.theglobalstatistics.com> > [Indian social media.com](#)

MOBILE APPS	PERCENTAGE
Chat Apps	91.60%
Social Networking Apps	89.50%
Entertainment & Video Apps	75.00%
Shopping Apps	72.20%
Maps Apps	67.60%
Game Apps	57.00%
Music Apps	53.60%
Health Apps	37.10%
Banking Apps	32.30%

Social media is a boon to society and community in general, by broadening the horizon of connectivity and understanding the world. With a single click of a button, an individual sees a wider range of spheres, as all the distances just vanish.

Youth in general are dominant and largest consumers of this platform. Further social media is offering democratization of knowledge and widening communication and as such enhancing their confidence and creativity. It connects people with ideas and possibilities, is now a days biggest device of education.

Digital activism is acting as a vehicle and transforming the society and community. Latest use of social media has been witnessed since the pandemic broke in 2019 in form of Sars- cov-2, when the whole world came to a standstill. People were forced to sit back at home and every economy suffered enormous losses. It was then social media came as a rescuer for office goers, teachers, children and many more. It offered platforms like *Cisco WebEx*, *Zoom*, *Google Meet* etc. for smooth functioning of different jobs, meetings and other works.

More and more are dependent on social medias for awareness and news happening around. One of the major benefits of social media is its outreach approach and closeness of loved ones staying in far off places, is not a hinderance anymore. Apart from these, it also plays a platform for the unemployed youth, as social media acts as an advertising hub for various opportunities in terms of employment, brand promotions etc.

To add more, the elder generations also look forward towards social media , for their connectivity with their loved ones living far away.

Media constitutes the 4th pillar of democracy. It plays an important role in keeping democracy alive and thriving. The role of the media is vital as a watchdog for uncovering errors and wrongdoings in the democracy. But we need these mediums for even more important reasons to amplify the crying rallies of the weak and curtail the trampling arrogance of the strong. Yes. It connected broken healthcare, breaking news, kind volunteers and depressed loved ones through a digital string in a way a lot of heads of states failed to do. (Insightpedia, 2021).

The role of social media in our society is very much a debatable issue. All technologies have their own pros and cons and express deleterious effects, which is also true for social media as well, as everything comes with a price and presents a gloomy picture in some cases too. When one flips the coin, this very social media acts like demon which is engulfing the mind of our future generation in a negative manner, playing havoc in their overall development-social, mental and physical well-being, thus acting as an inherent selfish giant.

One of the biggest drawbacks of social media is that it is depriving the youth and teenagers from outdoor activities, and keep them glued to itself only, leading to increase number of casualties like- suicide, depressions, sexual exploitation, abuse and what not. Children anymore do not want to share their talks, ideas and thoughts with their elderly, especially parents, and rely heavily on their peers for discussions and decisions, thus creating social isolation. These Gen X are, thus becoming more introvert, deprived of emotions, lacking empathy etc. One of the main reasons can be disintegration of families and lack of bond between them.

Secondly it leads to weakened self esteem in some youth and gives way to narcissism, by creating not so true notions. Thirdly in few cases women and children are trolled through cyber bullying for rapes, abductions etc.

II. CONCLUSION

As India is not a surveillance state, there must not be any illegal or unconstitutional check on the right to privacy and freedom of speech and expression which are the fundamental rights of every citizen. Social media awareness is needed which may enable citizens to be in a position to distinguish between truth and falsehood – and to know when democratic processes are being manipulated. There must be a balance as the Constitutions itself has provided several limitations on one's right to speech and expression. Social Media Platforms can provide safeguards in the event that democratic processes are being intentionally disrupted or harmful falsehoods are spreading, it can help people find out what is true.

Whether the concept of social media is helpful or of destructive nature depends on oneself.

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